

RABIES: AN OPPORTUNITY FOR STRAY DOG MANAGEMENT IN INDIA

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ABSTRACT

India hosts the world's largest stray dog population, making dog-mediated rabies a persistent public health and animal welfare challenge. Stray dogs not only face malnutrition, disease, and cruelty but also act as major vectors for rabies transmission, with India accounting for a significant proportion of global rabies deaths. While dog culling has proven ineffective, structured Dog Population Management (DPM) strategies such as Catch-Neuter-Vaccinate-Release (CNVR) programs, combined with Responsible Dog Ownership (RDO), offer sustainable solutions. Effective DPM requires systematic baseline surveys, adequate sterilisation and vaccination coverage, and regulation of food sources, while RDO emphasizes pet adoption, timely vaccination, accessible healthcare, and ethical care practices. Together, these measures can reduce free-roaming dog populations, prevent rabies spillover from wildlife, and mitigate human-animal conflicts. Such an approach can not only break rabies transmission cycles but also improve animal welfare, reduce human injuries and fatalities, and establish a framework for addressing issues posed by other stray animals in India.

KEYWORDS: Stray dog, Zoonosis, Animal-welfare, Vaccination, Ownership, Public Health

INTRODUCTION

India is the home to the largest stray animal population in the world. Stray dogs contribute the maximum to this population. This has resulted in dog-bite cases and cruelty towards stray animals being a common phenomenon, with videos of such events going viral on social and news media frequently. Stray animals live in extremely harsh conditions, are often malnourished and diseased, treated cruelly and have little to no exposure to healthcare. They are also vectors of many infectious diseases and cause environmental degradation. Dogs are the carriers of Rabies, a disease that remains incurable and endemic to many South-Asian and African countries, including India. India has set a goal of eliminating dog-mediated rabies by 2030 through its National Plan for the Elimination of Dog-Mediated Rabies (NAPRE). Here, we explore how this can be an opportunity to address and solve the stray dog problem in India.

STRAY DOGS IN INDIA

A stray animal is one that is allowed to roam freely, finds its own food, reproduces, and completes its life cycle on the streets. Stray animals can be feral, meaning they have no human contact, are wild, or have been disowned and left to roam. They may also be lost pets or owned by an individual or community that feeds them and allows them to roam freely. Most stray animals, being dogs, are referred to as Free Roaming Dogs (FRD). Dogs inhabit human settlements and are fed by people or food waste generated by communities, thereby acting as scavengers but also as carriers of diseases. This food is mostly insufficient, leading to malnourished and diseased animals. They become subject to human cruelty, making them aggressive towards humans, which causes bites in humans and injuries and death in both humans and dogs. FRDs are also a major traffic hazard throughout India, causing loss of life and property. Animal healthcare is poor in India, and targeting stray animals is abysmal, resulting in the average lifespan of street dogs

being extremely low at about 3.5 years in India. Dogs are territorial animals and are often involved in clashes with dogs of neighbouring territories and intruding dogs, which becomes a point of contact for transmission of infectious diseases such as rabies.

RABIES AND ITS RELATIONSHIP WITH STRAY DOGS

Rabies is an acute encephalitis caused by Lyssavirus and affects warm blooded animals, mostly mammals and rarely birds. 95% of world rabies deaths occur in Asia and Africa, 99% of which are caused by dogs. Almost all rabies deaths in America and Europe are due to wild animal bites. Rabies transmitted by dogs has been eliminated in most Western countries. This could be achieved because affluent societies can afford to keep pets, vaccinate them, and provide them with healthcare, which eliminates the stray animal and healthcare issues that pose major hindrances in economically challenged parts of the world. As Dogs are prone to frequent clashes, they transmit the virus among packs to maintain endemicity of the disease. Rabies can also spill over to dogs from wild animals. Therefore, effective Dog Population Management (DPM) programs and promoting Responsible Dog Ownership (RDO) are crucial to the elimination of rabies in India.

DOG POPULATION MANAGEMENT

Dog culling has been attempted in many parts of the world for DPM, but has largely remained ineffective as vacant dog territories are quickly replaced by rapidly reproducing dogs from other territories. Therefore, Animal Birth Control Programs (ABC), especially Catch, Neuter, Vaccinate and Release (CNVR) programs, have been more successful and are being implemented in India. However, proper identification and tagging of dogs, along with their subsequent release into their original territory, are key to the program's success. CNVR programs must be initiated after a proper baseline study of the FRD population and after assessing the degree

of intervention required. The sterilization and vaccination levels must be maintained by setting evidence-based targets that lead to an effective DPM. Limiting dogs' access to human food sources is also an effective tool for ABC and helps in reducing population turnover rates. Effective DPM can also promote health and prolong the lifespan of dogs, while decreasing the burden on CNVR programs. Sustained funding and an adequate number of trained personnel and infrastructure for keeping the program running till elimination is achieved.

Fig. 1: Illustrations of the Integrated approach to rabies elimination in India through dog population management and responsible ownership, leading to improved animal welfare and public health

RESPONSIBLE DOG OWNERSHIP

The goal must be to shift dogs from the streets to the homes of people willing to own them. Animal lovers should be encouraged to own pet dogs, take care of them, vaccinate them, adhere to vaccination schedules, and seek necessary healthcare for rabies prevention. Dog Owners need to be educated about responsible ownership practices, such as training their pets, understanding their pet's behaviour and needs, proper confinement of pets, and being vigilant in public places or when in contact with other people and pets to prevent human-animal and animal-animal conflicts. Animal healthcare must be made available, approachable and affordable to reduce ownership cost and encourage adoption. People must be educated about ethical and humane care of animals and the prevention of cruelty. With each dog being owned, taken care of, and vaccinated, rabies

elimination won't be a challenge, and the spread from wild animals to dogs can be prevented. There is also a need for awareness about dog licks and bite management in humans, including washing the infected site, seeking healthcare promptly, and vaccination, which will further reduce the risk of rabies.

CONCLUSION

Rabies elimination without a perpetually and universally vaccinated dog population is non-feasible. Stray dogs are a social and health hazard throughout the country. The rabies elimination program

presents an ideal opportunity to formulate and enforce laws, disseminate knowledge and awareness, and implement animal welfare programs in this regard. DPM, RDO, and rabies elimination are mutually dependent for the realization of dog-mediated rabies elimination and have the added advantage of preventing other dog-mediated diseases, human-dog conflict, and losses in life and property caused by dogs. It can also lay the foundation and establish a framework for managing other stray animals, such as cats and cattle.

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